

Comparison of Simulations of Neutron Noise Induced by Mechanical Vibrations in a 2D Simplified UOX Assembly

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ABSTRACT

In the last decade, several simulation tools have been developed to compute the neutron noise produced by different perturbations inside nuclear reactors, using either deterministic or Monte Carlo methods. In this work, we compare a set of such solvers for a benchmark configuration involving a simplified UOX fuel assembly with a vibrating pin-cell. High-fidelity methods, encompassing deterministic and Monte Carlo solvers, yield consistent results for the first noise harmonic. Low-fidelity (SP_N) solvers fail to accurately describe the noise field close to the perturbation, as expected. A novel non-perturbative Monte Carlo solver, which allows foregoing the 'orthodox linearization', is also used to assess higher-order noise harmonics.

Keywords: Neutron noise, Monte Carlo, Simplified spherical harmonics approximation, Mechanical vibrations.

1. INTRODUCTION

Neutron noise in nuclear power reactors is defined as the small fluctuations of the neutron flux around its time-average, due to small perturbations of the core. Such fluctuations carry useful information that can be used in reactor core diagnosis [1]. For this purpose, it is of utmost importance to develop accurate numerical tools for the simulation of the neutron noise produced by different types of perturbations. Over the last decade, several simulation codes have been independently developed to solve the neutron noise equations, in particular within the framework of the CORTEX H2020 European project [2]. These include a variety of numerical solvers, using e.g. transport theory (based on either deterministic or Monte Carlo methods), diffusion theory, or intermediate approximations. A comparative investigation of such simulation tools has been carried out in Ref. 3 and 4, covering the majority of codes then available, based on a benchmark configuration involving mechanical vibrations in a two-dimensional UOX fuel assembly, with a simplified geometry. This study showed that high-fidelity solvers are capable of correctly simulating the noise field (within the limits of validity of the 'orthodox linearization' of the noise equations [5]), whereas solvers based on the diffusion approximation might incur the same accuracy issues as in standard reactor physics problems.

In this work, we set out to extend the analysis of Ref. 4, by including a larger spectrum of noise solvers. On the deterministic side, we consider the SP_N capabilities of FEMFFUSION [6, 7], in both the time and frequency domain, in view of overcoming the aforementioned diffusion limitations. On the Monte Carlo side, we consider a novel non-perturbative approach in the frequency domain that has been recently developed in the MGMC mini-app [8, 9] in order to forego the first-order approximation inherent in the 'orthodox linearization'. In the following sections, we will present the preliminary results concerning the comparisons of several noise simulation codes to revisit the same benchmark problem as in Ref. 4.

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2. METHODS AND TOOLS

We briefly describe the neutron noise solvers used in this work, and the simplified UOX fuel assembly configuration chosen as a benchmark for the comparison of the simulation results.

2.1. FEMFFUSION-TD/FD

FEMFFUSION is an open-source deterministic code that solves the multi-group neutron diffusion and simplified spherical harmonics (SP_N) equations, both in the time domain (TD) and in the frequency domain (FD) [6, 7]. The time-domain diffusion solver was previously considered in Ref. 4, whereas the other solvers are applied to this benchmark for the first time. In the time domain, FEMFFUSION-TD uses a fixed spatial grid, refined around the region of the mechanical perturbation, whose macroscopic cross sections at every time step are determined by the position of the vibrating fuel pin. Notably, the variation of the diffusion coefficient is taken into account. Computations are carried out over three periods. A fast-Fourier transform is then applied to convert the results to the frequency domain. In the frequency domain, FEMFFUSION-FD solves the linearized neutron noise equations, and uses the ' ε/d ' model for the mechanical vibration [4].

2.2. The IDT Lattice Solver in APOLLO3

The IDT lattice solver of the deterministic code APOLLO3[®] [10] allows for linear noise calculations in the frequency domain. Using the discrete ordinates method and the method of short characteristics, it tackles the set of equations for the real and imaginary parts of the noise field. In Ref. 4, APOLLO3-IDT was taken as a reference for the deterministic calculations. Mechanical vibrations are modeled with the ' ε/d ' approximation [4]. In this work, we use the discrete ordinates method of order S_{16} .

2.3. The Noise Solvers in the MGMC Monte Carlo Mini-app

The open-source Monte Carlo mini-app MGMC [11] includes two different noise solvers in the frequency domain: a legacy solver for the linearized noise equation [12] (which has been previously tested on this benchmark), and a novel non-perturbative noise (NPN) solver. The NPN approach does not resort to the linearization of the noise equation [8, 9]. Instead, it solves the noise equations for all harmonics simultaneously, by considering the angular frequency as an additional dimension explored by noise particles. The noise equation is reformulated as an eigenvalue problem, solved by power iteration. Additionally, MGMC features an exact noise source sampling, which allows modeling the vibration without approximations [12].

2.4. A Two-dimensional Simplified UOX Fuel Assembly Benchmark for Neutron Noise

To compare our neutron noise solvers, we rely on the first problem of the benchmark described in Ref. 4, whose main features are recalled below. A two-dimensional simplified UOX fuel assembly is used, with reflective boundaries (see Fig. 1). It includes 264 homogeneous square fuel pins and 25 water holes. The assembly side is 21.58 cm, including a 0.08 cm thick water blade. A two-group energy structure is used. Details and nuclear data can be found in Ref. 4. For the neutron noise simulations, the fuel pin identified in Fig. 1 with a blue circle vibrates sinusoidally along the x axis, with amplitude 0.2 cm at frequency $\omega_0/2\pi = 1$ Hz. To simplify visualization, our simulation results will correspond to the noise field along the horizontal line that crosses the vibrating pin in its center, at $y = 8.27$ cm.

The fiducial quantity chosen for the comparison of the noise solvers is the complex-valued neutron noise $\delta\phi_g$ in the fast ($g = 1$) and thermal ($g = 2$) energy group. In addition, since linear neutron noise solvers rely on the computation of the steady state, we will also determine the neutron flux ϕ_g and the associated multiplication factor k_{eff} in the static configuration. Noise field results are normalized by the

Figure 1. The simplified UOX fuel assembly chosen as a benchmark configuration. The fuel pin vibrating along the x axis is identified by a blue circle. The reference row to display the noise field is shown as a dotted line.

integral of their corresponding steady-state flux.

The discrepancies among solvers are assessed using $\Delta k_{\text{eff}} = k_{\text{eff}} - k_{\text{eff}}^{\text{ref}}$, $\text{RMSE}(\phi) = \text{RMSE}(\phi|\phi^{\text{ref}})$ and $\text{RMSE}(\delta\phi) = \text{RMSE}(\delta\phi|\delta\phi^{\text{ref}})$, where the reference values $k_{\text{eff}}^{\text{ref}}$, ϕ_g^{ref} and $\delta\phi_g^{\text{ref}}$ are those computed with the linear solver of MGMC. The root mean square errors are defined as

$$\text{RMSE}(\psi|\psi') = \frac{\|\psi - \psi'\|_2}{\|\psi'\|_2} \quad \text{where} \quad \|\psi\|_2^2 = \sum_{g,j,k} |\psi_g(x_j, y_k)|^2 \delta x_j \delta y_k,$$

where g, j, k run through the groups and the mesh indices, and $\delta x_j \delta y_k$ is the surface of an element of the mesh. As MGMC results are given on a slightly different spatial mesh, values on the benchmark's mesh have been obtained by bilinear interpolation. For the MGMC–Linear solver, statistical uncertainty is provided by in-code estimates, while for the MGMC–NPN solver a reliable estimate for the statistical uncertainty has been obtained using 25 independent replicas [8, 9].

3. NUMERICAL SIMULATION RESULTS

3.1. Analysis of the Steady State Configuration

Solvers addressing the linearized noise equation in the frequency domain (APOLLO3–IDT, FEMFFUSION–FD) directly compute the critical flux. In MGMC–NPN, the steady state corresponds to the 0th harmonic component of the noise field (i.e., the time-average of the flux). In Fig. 2 we display the steady-state neutron flux for all solvers, along the line at $y = 8.27$ cm, and the relative differences with respect to the MGMC–linear solver, taken as a reference. The RMSE of the relative differences and the computed k_{eff} are summarized in Tab. I. APOLLO3–IDT, MGMC–linear and MGMC–NPN methods yield coherent results. As expected, the SP_1 results of FEMFFUSION show a significant discrepancy, which is reduced as the SP_N order increases.

3.2. Analysis of the First Harmonic of the Neutron Noise

The comparison of the first harmonic of the noise field, i.e., the component at $\omega = \omega_0$ (1 Hz), is presented in Fig. 3. The imaginary part of the noise field is the dominant component, because the noise source is also imaginary for the first harmonic (due to the convention on the phase). Two spikes can be clearly identified, corresponding to the two oscillating interfaces of the vibrating fuel pin. The high-fidelity solvers APOLLO3–IDT, MGMC–linear and MGMC–NPN yield coherent results. The diffusion-like SP_N

Figure 2. Comparison of the steady-state neutron flux. The relative difference is also displayed, using MGMC-Linear as a reference.

Table I. Comparison between codes for the steady-state configuration.

CODE	k_{eff}	Δk_{eff} (pcm)	RMSE(ϕ)	RMSE($\delta\phi_{\omega_0}$)	RMSE($\delta\phi_{2\omega_0}$)
FEMFFUSION FD-SP ₁	1.01368	1450	1.31	30.48	66.96
FEMFFUSION FD-SP ₃	1.00870	952	1.01	23.14	35.56
FEMFFUSION FD-SP ₅	1.00531	614	0.82	18.26	8.91
FEMFFUSION FD-SP ₇	1.00302	385	0.68	16.16	12.62
APOLLO-IDT	0.99934	16	0.26	23.13	30.74
MGMC-Linear*	0.99918(3)	–	–	–	–
MGMC-NPN*	0.99918(1)	<1	0.01	52.05	138.91

* Statistical uncertainties are provided in parentheses. RMSE are given in percent.

solvers of FEMFFUSION highly underestimate the noise near the vibrating pin, but yield values similar to the higher-fidelity solvers far from the perturbation, where neutron detectors are more likely to be located. For the sake of completeness, the amplitude $|\delta\phi|/\phi$ of the neutron noise relative to the steady state is shown in Fig. 4. In Fig. 5 we focus then on FEMFFUSION simulations, in the time and frequency domain, with various SP_N approximations. For a given order of SP_N, the results of the FD and TD approaches are similar. Close to the vibrating pin, different SP_N orders yield strikingly different results; however, all fail to reproduce the findings of higher-fidelity solvers. These discrepancies decrease far

from the perturbation, which is coherent with previous results for oscillating cross sections [7].

(a) Fast neutron noise, real part.

(b) Thermal neutron noise, real part.

(c) Fast neutron noise, imaginary part.

(d) Thermal neutron noise, imaginary part.

Figure 3. Comparison of the first harmonic of the noise field: real and imaginary parts.

(a) Relative amplitude of fast neutron noise.

(b) Relative amplitude of thermal neutron noise.

Figure 4. Comparison of the amplitude of the neutron noise relative to the steady state for the first harmonic.

Figure 5. Focus on FEMFFUSION time domain and frequency domain calculations in the diffusion-like approximations: relative amplitude of the first harmonic of the noise field, compared to the steady state.

3.3. Analysis of the Second Harmonic of the Neutron Noise

We have also examined the second harmonic of the noise field, at $\omega = 2\omega_0$ (2 Hz). The results for the amplitude of the relative neutron noise are compared in Fig. 6, while the real and imaginary parts of the noise field are presented in Fig. 7. The noise field is approximately in phase quadrature with the first harmonic, and the real part is the dominant component. The amplitude of the second harmonic is smaller than that of the first harmonic in the vicinity of the perturbation, but larger far from the perturbation, as already observed in previous studies [12]. APOLLO3-IDT, MGMC-linear and high-order FEMFFUSION-FD computations show good agreement far from the vibration, but they present significant differences otherwise. The diffusion approximation (SP₁) fails to reproduce this result in the far-field. The case of the MGMC-NPN computation is of special interest. Indeed, a significant discrepancy on the second harmonic is obtained (as expected) when using a non-perturbative approach, mostly due to the coupling between the first and the second harmonic [9], which reduces the noise amplitude in the far-field. Unfortunately, we have not been able to obtain accurate results for the second harmonic FEMFFUSION-TD, due to numerical instabilities in the time-domain computation. Thus, at present we sorely lack an independent non-perturbative simulation to corroborate the MGMC-NPN results, which should not be considered conclusive until confirmed by additional studies.

Figure 6. Comparison of the amplitude of the neutron noise relative to the steady state for the second harmonic.

Figure 7. Comparison of the second harmonic of the noise field: real and imaginary parts.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study extends the comparison of different neutron noise solvers applied to the simulation of a vibrating fuel pin in a simplified UOX assembly benchmark, previously considered in Ref. 4.

High-fidelity (deterministic and Monte Carlo) methods produce coherent results for the first harmonic of the noise field. The NPN Monte Carlo solver of MGMC is in good agreement with the legacy MGMC solver for the linearized noise equation, which builds confidence in the novel NPN approach. The FEMFFUSION implementations of SP_N formulations reproduce the first harmonic with reasonable accuracy in regions sufficiently far from the perturbation, both with time-dependent and frequency-dependent simulations. This holds true even for SP_1 , i.e. the diffusion approximation. However, SP_N solvers exhibit noticeable deviations in the vicinity of the vibrating pin, where strong spatial gradients of the noise occur. Also, higher-order SP_N solvers do not converge to the reference, a behavior that also occurs in the steady-state calculations due to the modeling limitations of the SP_N approximation [7].

For the second harmonic, MGMC-NPN is different from MGMC-linear, as expected, whereas APOLLO3-IDT aligns with MGMC-linear (both use the 'orthodox' approximation). We currently lack a comparison for MGMC-NPN coming from an independently developed non-perturbative noise solver, which would be especially valuable. Diffusion seems to fail even in the far-field, whereas higher-order SP_7 solvers bring a significant improvement and recover results similar to those of higher-fidelity methods. Future work should address the issues of time-domain computation of the second harmonic, and more broadly investigate non-perturbative approaches to the noise equations.

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